

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING USING CELLULAR CONCRETE: DEVELOPMENT OF AN OPTIMIZED LOW-COST FOAM GENERATOR AND ASPECTS RELATED TO SURFACTANTS EFFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a study on the development and optimization of a simple and low-cost foam generator device designed as a system component to produce lightweight mortar suitable for use in additive manufacturing. The project guidelines are the repeatability of the foam characteristics, continuous production, low cost to build the equipment, and targeting the surfactant's maximum efficiency. After an introduction about air incorporation in cementitious materials, addressing the main methods and equipment for foam production present in literature, the details of the project, its calibration process and the obtained results are presented. The quality criteria attributed to the foam that measure the efficiency of the device are quantified and discussed. For each device configuration, the variation in the produced foam volume, target density and bubble stability were documented. The results show a relation on the foam quality linked to the outlet nozzle diameter variation as well as the amount of foaming agent employed in the water solution. The foam obtained with the highest quality had a production rate of 70ml/s, density of 43.43kg/m³ and a drainage amount of 4ml for 500ml of foam at rest for 5 minutes. The study demonstrates that despite the use of a low and constant air pressure of 5.80psi, obtained through a small electromagnetic air compressor, the target foam quality was successfully achieved. As a result, a methodology could be established to obtain the best foam regardless of the surfactant used. Because it is a small, low-cost and easy-to-build device, since many components are made by 3D printing, it can be useful in research for the development of lightweight cementitious materials on the bench that require smaller amounts of foam.

KEYWORDS: Foam Generator, Additive Manufacturing, Foam Concrete

I. INTRODUCTION

The air incorporation into cementitious materials is a practice that presents benefits both in handling the fresh state material and in the hard state product performance, having low density and consequently weight reduction as an important parameter observed [1]. Other than the void creation by air incorporation, lightweight concretes can be obtained as well by adding low-density aggregates in the cementitious system. In this sense, concretes with specific mass below 1800 kg/m³ can be named as lightweight [2]. Jones [3] consider that a conventional density for lightweight concretes with incorporated air, or cellular concretes (CC), presents values between 500-1600 kg/m³. Ultralight concretes, on the other hand, present densities lower than 500 kg/m³. This wide range of densities, starting from 150 kg/m³ makes this material desirable due to its versatility in several applications. Properties such as reduced weight, fire resistance, sound absorption and thermal insulation are related to the void area and helps to meet the performance requirements for different application [4]. Insulating

panels, soil stabilization, screeds, road subgrade, slabs and large bricks are just some of the many possibilities that CC can be applied [5].

According to [6], the various methods for generating foam can be classified in two groups: the first one is surfactant based and creates bubbles, mainly by agitation and depressurization, using air from the atmosphere. The second group is based on additions such as aluminium powder, which reacts with calcium hydroxide present in the cement matrix during hydration, generating hydrogen gas and promoting spontaneous aeration. The foam generation by agitation or other methods based on surfactants are already consolidated strategies for producing cellular concrete [7]. However, experiments have shown that despite the surfactants manufacturer's recommendations, the results can vary depending on the equipment, production method, temperature, water used, etc. In this sense, the development of the device shown in this article establishes a test routine, creating a methodology that helps to achieve the quality control for CC foam production and targeting the maximum performance of the employed surfactant.

Considering the need to produce an optimized CC for use in additive manufacturing, a foam-generating device specifically designed for operating with surfactants in aqueous media was developed. This choice is justified by the disadvantages of the spontaneous foam generation method. In addition to being more expensive, it requires an autoclaving curing process (high-pressure steam) to obtain the expected quality, thus adding a limitation to the production of parts by additive manufacturing [8].

The device development takes fixed and variable parameters as a guideline. Experiments were carried out with gradual changes in specific parameters to explore the foam quality variation until the best results could be obtained and set. After this stage, adjustments were made only to the foam formulation to increase stability and production rate. The core operation of the presented equipment takes advantage of agitation by pressurized atomization, followed by depressurization. The result is a foam that meets regulatory requirements. According to ASTM C796/C796M – 12 [9], the foam density for cellular concrete can vary between 30kg/m^3 and 65kg/m^3 . However, a low-quality foam, as measured by untargeted density and stability, can lead good strategies for CC quality improvement to fail. Thus, mixing additions and fibers into the CC system to improve the mechanical strength could be wasteful if the foam reports low-quality aspects [4]. The effort to meet the best performance from the surfactants is mainly due to the application dynamics required by the additive manufacturing process which will subject CC to pumping, additivation, homogenization and deposition in layers. In this sense, the use of a properly stable foam, capable of remaining stable when incorporated into the cementitious matrix, is mandatory.

For a better understanding of the air bubbles formation process, a closer look on the surfactant's molecular scale inside a water solution is required. Its amphiphilic nature means that it has molecules with two opposite ends composed as polar and non-polar. The polar group is hydrophilic and has affinity for water and other polar compounds. The nonpolar group is hydrophobic and has an affinity for oily substances and other nonpolar compounds. The surfactants solution makes the water's surface tension to decrease by replacing some surface molecules with nonpolar groups [11]. Thus, from a certain concentration of surfactant, when subjected to agitation, the molecules tend to organize themselves into a spherical shape, trapping air in a liquid interface on a nanometric scale, forming a film called a lamella. The bubbles then organize themselves in sizes ranging from a few micrometers to centimeters [10].

Figure 1. Surfactant molecule (a); Bubble molecular structure (b); adapted from [12]

Once the foam is formed, one of the crucial phenomena for its maintenance is associated with the surfactant solution drainage on the lamellar surface, which represents the cause of greater instability. In a foam, the contact between the lamella is called the Plateau border. These regions form small channels with a resulting curvature from the difference between the size of the bubbles, creating an area of lower pressure that attracts the lamellar liquid, thus, promoting drainage. In addition to drainage and evaporation, which are factors that also reduce the lamellar thickness, accelerating the bubbles collapse, another important phenomenon that also deteriorates the initial configuration of the formed foam is the coalescence. This happens when smaller bubbles merge with larger ones, resulting in a reduction in the total contact surface area between them. When this happens, the energy level of the system is reduced, reducing the lamellar thickness and facilitating deterioration [4]. Increasing the viscosity of the surfactant-containing solution and creating foam with smaller and more uniform bubbles can help to last the lamellar thickness and foam stability for longer.

It should be noticed that the air bubbles mechanisms described are valid for the foam on its own. When it is incorporated into the cementitious matrix, it becomes part of a three-phase system, presenting new interaction mechanisms [10]. The bubble incorporation in a cementitious matrix is a dynamic process and not exactly related to the proportions of foam added to the system. With the bubbles separated from each other by the mortar, there are changes in the way the foam behaves and is distributed [3]. Although this interaction has its own characteristics, the quality of the foam used is crucial to obtaining a CC with the expected performance in both the fresh and hardened state.

II. WORK ORGANIZATION

This article is organized in a systemic sequence as follows: after an introduction about air incorporation in cementitious materials, addressing the foam production mechanism, the main methods for foam production are presented. In the methodology section the details of the foam generator device as well as the calibration process and the results obtained are presented. The next section shows the results and discusses the strategy for fine tuning the surfactant solution and targeting its best performance.

III. OBJECTIVES

This paper's main objective is to present a study on the development of a low-cost device optimized for generating high quality foam for cementitious materials incorporation. The specific objective is to present a methodology that helps to target the maximum efficiency from a given surfactant, generating a stable foam with a density within the norm and with an ideal production rate for small-scale experiments.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The development of the foam generating system followed an experimental methodology in which two stages were established. The first (stage 1) aimed to identify the concentration dosage of the foaming agent solution diluted in water that would produce the best foam quality. The second (stage 2) selected the best values obtained in the first stage to improve the foam stability with new experiments based on the surfactant concentration.

4.1. FOAM GENERATOR DEVICE

Based on technical and efficiency requirements, a portable, low-cost, easy-to-handle foam generating device was built. It can produce high-quality foam in quantities below 5 liters per minute, making it affordable for laboratory bench experiments. According to [4] an appropriate device needs to be able to produce foam through a turbulent flow generating high shear stress. This is possible through agitation strategies using high-speed mechanical paddles, as well as the use of compressed air forcing the water and surfactant solution through a turbulent path. The main advantages of using a compressed air system are the continuous production and the shorter time needed to produce the foam of the desired quality. In addition, the compressed air can drive the foam through a pipe, making it easier to be directly placed on the cementitious matrix for incorporation and production of the cellular concrete.

The design of the device consists of a five-component system as follows. The surfactant solution with the desired dilution is placed in a **reservoir**. A **peristaltic pump** then delivers this solution through a

hose to a splitter. An electromagnetic **air compressor** delivers the air, which connects to the splitter. Upon receiving the air at high speed, the solution is atomized and moved into a cylindrical shearing chamber (**wand**) containing a sponge made of stainless-steel wires where the foam is produced. At the end of this chamber, a **nozzle** is attached to restrict the outlet, slightly raising the pressure inside the wand chamber and delivering the foam ready for use. Except for the air compressor and the reservoir, the system's components were developed using digital fabrication and manual labour for assembly, the most complex of which is the peristaltic surfactant dosing pump.

Figure 2. Foam generator device (a); Foam production (b)

4.2. FIXED AND VARIABLE PARAMETERS

The fixed parameters for the experiments in stage 1 were the compressed air, the dilution of the surfactant and the size of the wand. The variable parameters consist of the solution dosage for the foaming agent/water and the diameter of the outlet nozzle. Experiments were carried out with eight different dosages for each nozzle diameter, with three data collections each to obtain an average. The nozzle outlet diameters taken were 5mm, 7mm, 10mm, 15mm, 20mm and 25mm. The 5mm and 25mm nozzles were not considered as they produced foam densities out of the normative range.

Table 1. Fixed parameters

Compressed air	125L/min.; 5.8psi
Surfactant dilution	1:40 (surfactant x water)
Cylindrical wand	15cm in length; 3cm internal diameter
Stainless-steel sponge	20g

The foam quality was determined by the density and stability obtained in the experiments. The densities were referenced by the normative [9] and measurements were taken with a 1000ml container which was filled with the produced foam, timed and weighed. The procedure used to fill and measure the containers is similar as described in the literature [4]. The wand was placed close to the bottom and rises as the produced foam fills the container, ensuring that there were no voids. In this same experiment, the foam production rates in ml/second could be measured for each dosage of solution. The foam stability was measured using a graduated cylindrical container filled with 500ml of foam and left to stand for 5 minutes. After this time, the amount of liquid drained because of the deterioration of the bubbles was measured. The lower the amount of liquid, the greater the stability of the foam. Foams were produced with eight different dosages, varying the amount of surfactant solution from 90ml to 368ml, according to the minimum and maximum speeds of the peristaltic pump developed. The synthetic foaming agent Centripor SK 100 from MC Bauchemie was used in all the experiments. The dilution used in stage 1 followed the manufacturer's recommendation of 1:40 (foaming agent/water).

4.3. PERISTALTIC PUMP DEVELOPMENT

Peristaltic pumps are mechanisms used in various applications where it is necessary to move a fluid with controlled flow and stand out for their simplicity, compact size and small number of components when compared to other systems [10]. This pump employs the principle of peristalsis, where a flexible hose undergoes pressing and relaxing movements in a controlled manner, pressurizing the contents of the hose in the desired direction. The material contact takes place only inside the hose, thus facilitating the cleaning of the equipment and the integrity of the material used, keeping it free from contamination. This project used two **nema 17** stepper motors, coupled to **3 gears** creating a reduction to increase torque. The main shaft moves a **rotor** with two points of contact with the **hose** equipped with **rollers** made from type 608z bearings. The **stator** has an interchangeable **housing**, making it compatible for hoses with external diameters between 5 and 10mm.

Figure 3. Peristaltic pump parts (a); Electronics assembly (b)

The equipment's interface is driven by an Arduino uno microcontroller programmed with a 141 lines script to display the speed in RPM, percentage and direction as clockwise and counterclockwise on an LCD screen, thus making it easier to document the experiments and calibrate the solution dosing. To work properly with the desired durability, the hose needs to be kneaded precisely, so that the distance between the roller face and the kneading wall is equivalent to the sum of the walls of the hose used, ensuring that the pressure occurs. This project was developed using spare parts available in the laboratory for cost reduction. However, it is possible to create an equivalent equipment even more simple and at a lower cost. Even so, this equipment proved to be robust and reliable.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. DATA COLLECTION

The results collected in step 1 were organized into two charts for each nozzle used. The densities and stability of the foam obtained according to the different dosages of solution injected into the system were measured, as well as the production rate in ml/second shown in the tables.

dosage vs Density (7mm nozzle - 30mm wand)

(a)

Foam stability (7mm nozzle)

(b)

Figure 4. Density data for the 7mm nozzle (a); Stability data for the 7mm nozzle (b)

dosage vs Density (10mm nozzle - 30mm wand)

(a)

Foam stability (10mm nozzle)

(b)

Figure 5. Density data for the 10mm nozzle (a); Stability data for the 10mm nozzle (b)

dosage vs Density (15mm nozzle - 30mm wand)

(a)

Foam stability (15mm nozzle)

(b)

Figure 6. Density data for the 15mm nozzle (a); Stability data for the 15mm nozzle (b)

Table 2. 7mm nozzle

Dosage mililiters	Production rate ml/sec.
90	25,06
130	36,54
165	47,01
203	55,01
250	67,84
273	75,19
313	80,13
368	92,64

Table 3. 10mm nozzle

Dosage mililiters	Production rate ml/sec.
90	26,39
130	37,36
165	48,57
203	57,02
250	68,80
273	77,57
313	81,05
368	93,46

Table 4. 15mm nozzle

Dosage mililiters	Production rate ml/sec.
90	28,32
130	39,87
165	52,82
203	57,93
250	78,52
273	83,31
313	85,11
368	94,65

dosage vs Density (20mm nozzle - 30mm wand)

(a)

Foam stability (20mm nozzle)

(b)

Figure 7. Density data for the 20mm nozzle (a); Stability data for the 20mm nozzle (b)

dosage vs Density (25mm nozzle - 30mm wand)

(a)

Foam stability (25mm nozzle)

(b)

Figure 8. Density data for the 25mm nozzle (a); Stability data for the 25mm nozzle (b)

Table 5. 20mm nozzle

Dosage ml	Production rate ml/sec.
90	29,62
130	41,44
165	55,27
203	59,95
250	80,23
273	85,57
313	92,40
368	97,56

Table 6. 25mm nozzle

Dosage ml	Production rate ml/sec.
90	31,98
130	43,81
165	57,71
203	61,44
250	84,99
273	88,63
313	96,62
368	107,58

4.1. DISCUSSION

It was observed that the use of different nozzles delivers different results given the fixed parameters. Regarding the densities obtained, the 7 and 10mm nozzles produced some foams of more than 65kg/m³, while the others managed to stay within the norm for all the dosages used. In terms of foam stability, it was observed that the larger nozzles tend to produce less stable the foam. Regarding the rate of foam production, larger nozzles produce more foam over the same period. In addition to the data collected by measurement, during the experiments the visual and tactile aspect of the foams produced was more fragile, with bubbles appearing larger when larger nozzles were used, specially the 20 and 25mm ones. This observation was justified by the stability measurements.

After collecting the results, the 7mm nozzle and the 203mm/min dosage were chosen as the fixed parameters because they had a good relationship between density, stability and production rate. This configuration delivered a 56.8kg/m³ foam at a production rate of 55.01 ml/second and produced approximately 5ml of drained liquid for the 1:40 surfactant/water concentration. With this configuration and in compliance with what was established in stage 1, stage 2 followed, using the new fixed parameters to improve the foam by modifying its formulation. The experiments planned for stage 2 included new measurements for density, stability and production rate for the dilution parameters of the foaming agent higher and lower than initially used. Experiments were carried out with dilutions of 1:10 to 1:50 parts surfactant to water. The results showed that increasing the surfactant concentration made the foam lighter, more stable with an increased production rate. The best results were obtained for the 1:10 concentration. according to the graphs below:

Figure 9. Density data vs surfactant concentration (a); Stability data vs surfactant concentration (b)

Figure 10. Production rate according to different surfactant concentration

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This article presents a study on the development of low-cost equipment to produce optimized foam for incorporation into cellular concrete. The core mechanisms, responsible for the dynamics of bubble formation and degradation, were presented as well as the technical details of the equipment developed. Experiments were carried out progressively to select the best parameters for the equipment, such as dosage and nozzle diameter, as well as the best surfactant dilution for the formulation used. The resulting foam from this optimization showed 43.43KG/m³ with slow degradation, measuring 4ml of drainage per 500ml in 5 minutes and a production rate of 71,42ml/sec. proving to be suitable for producing cellular concrete below 500kg/m³. The device presented is part of a complete low-cost system being developed for the additive manufacture of cellular concrete. With the results obtained, it was possible to validate the equipment. It is hoped that this study will facilitate the conduction of further research on cellular concrete by the community taking advantage of the affordability to the equipment.

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